

Bioactive glass (45S5)-based 3D scaffolds coated with magnesium and zinc-loaded hydroxyapatite nanoparticles for tissue engineering applications

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Abstract

Bioactive glass (BG) -based scaffolds of 45S5 composition covered with hydroxyapatite nanoparticles loaded with Mg²⁺, Zn²⁺ and, both Mg²⁺ and Zn²⁺ ions, were tested as materials

for tissue engineering uses. The scaffolds were prepared by the foam replica technique and mono metal and bimetal-loaded and unloaded hydroxyapatite nanoparticles (HA, Zn-HA, Mg-HA and Mg-Zn-HA) were obtained by an adaptation of the wet chemical deposition method. Coating of BG with these nanoparticles was performed by dip-coating to obtain HA-BG, Zn-HA-BG, Mg-HA-BG and Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds.

As predictors of *in vivo* bioactivity of the produced scaffolds, in this study we investigated the formation of an apatite layer on the scaffold in the presence of simulated body fluid and the cytotoxicity and osteogenic properties of the materials *in vitro* using osteoblastic MG-63 cell cultures and focusing on the evaluation of cell-material contact (adherence), cell viability, and proliferation. The mineralization assay following Kokubo's protocol indicated that two metal loaded Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds exhibited higher/faster bioactivity than one-metal loaded scaffolds while mineralization of HA-BG, Zn-HA-BG and Mg-HA-BG scaffolds was similar to that of uncoated scaffolds. Moreover, an increase in biocompatibility and proliferation of MG-63 cells after 48 h and 7 days as evaluated by WST-1 and BrdU-assays, was observed for Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds, in agreement with SEM images showing a better interaction between these scaffolds and cells, than those observed for one metal-loaded HA-coated scaffolds. Altogether, the obtained results suggest that nanocrystalline Mg-Zn-HA coatings enhance the biological performance of standard BG scaffolds of 45S5 composition.

1. Introduction

The performance of biomaterials used to replace lost structures and promote new tissue formation is governed by their ability to induce *angiogenesis* and stimulate *osteogenesis*. [1] To date, calcium phosphates mostly as derivatives of hydroxyapatite (HA; $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$) and tricalcium phosphate (TCP; $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$) are among the most commonly used synthetic bone substitutes. [2] These materials are known to show good osteoconductive properties but limited stimulation of osteogenic differentiation, deficient surface reactivity and either a fast or a too slow resorption in clinical uses. [3]

The major calcium phosphate component of bone is not a chemically homogenous material, but incorporates trace elements (Na^+ , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Si^{4+} , Sr^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , among others) whose vital roles in the formation, growth, and repair of bone is well documented. [4,5] In *in vivo* conditions, bone apatite efficiently exchange Ca^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} ions with CO_3^{2-} , F^- , Cl^- , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , and K^+ ions present in physiological fluids, which are believed to be one of the reasons for the changes in crystallinity, solubility, and biological response of bone apatite. Doping of synthesized HA with Na^+ , K^+ , Ba^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ti^{4+} , Cu^{2+} , Si^{2+} , F^- , Cl^- , $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ significantly change the lattice parameters and cell volume of HA crystal in native and sintered state, resulting in different types of crystal defect and surface charge distribution. [6] Therefore, changes in the original absorption and release of bioactive molecules, degradability, mineralization, and biological response of HA are expected. In fact, hydroxyapatites in the nanometer regime with increasing content of ion substitution in the crystal lattice and of reduced crystallinity were reported to promote osteoblast adhesion, controlled degradation, increased osteoconductive properties, and increased mechanical

strength.[7,8] At the same time some of dissolved ions also have angiogenic and osteogenic properties, such as Mg^{+2} and Zn^{+2} . [9–13]

A variety of synthesis methods have been employed to produce Mg, Sr, Mn, Fe, Zn, and Ag-doped calcium phosphate materials, showing crystalline, morphological and stoichiometric characteristics strongly depending on the production method.[14,15] Among the doping metal ions of interest are Sr^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Fe^{2+}/Fe^{3+} , which are known for their anabolic effects in bone metabolism in the human body. Also, dissolved Si as $Si(OH)_4$ is essential for metabolic processes, formation, and calcification of bone tissue.[16]

Another very relevant group of biomaterials for bone regeneration are bioactive glasses (BGs), which can be made into 3D scaffolds of suitable porosity for bone regeneration.[17] In particular, the most frequently used BG is the so-called 45S5BG of composition 45% SiO_2 , 24.5% Na_2O , 24.5% CaO , and 6% P_2O_5 (in w%) which has been shown to exhibit rapid formation of a carbonate-substituted hydroxyapatite-like layer on its surface both *in vitro* and *in vivo* providing bonding to bone and surrounding tissues.[18] 45S5BG is an osteo stimulating material which presents also angiogenic effects,[19,20] and are capable of inducing angiogenic and osteogenic differentiation of stem cells by release of bioactive ions.[21] Among several approaches reported in the literature to further improve the osteogenic properties of bioactive glass scaffolds, the synthesis of calcium phosphates/BG composite materials appears a promising strategy.[3]

In particular, the incorporation of ion-doped HA particles onto BG scaffolds seems a convenient approach to enhance the surface functionalities of scaffolds. In the present study we report the synthesis and *in vitro* biological evaluation of highly porous (>90%) foam-like 45S5 BG structures coated with mono and bimetal-doped HA (Zn^{2+} and Mg^{2+}) designed to improve mechanical properties, structure, and biocompatibility of HA/BG composites for

tissue engineering uses. Among the important conditions to be fulfilled by the scaffold is the appropriate surface properties for cell adhesion, proliferation and differentiation. For assessment of bioactivity of the metal-doped HA-BG composites, in this study we investigated the formation of an apatite layer on the scaffold in the presence of simulated body fluid (SBF) and the cytotoxicity and osteogenic properties of the materials *in vitro* using osteoblastic MG-63 cell cultures and focusing on the evaluation of cell-material contact (adherence), cell viability, and proliferation.

2. Materials and Methods

2.a Materials

Bioactive glass of 45S5 composition (SCHOTT Ag, Standort Landshut) in powder form and an average particle size of $\sim 4 \mu\text{m}$, was used. A Fully reticulated polyester-based polyurethane (PU) foam with 60 ppi (Eurofoam Deutschland GmbH) was used as sacrificial template. All chemicals used in the assays (see S.I Chemicals) are of analytical grade and were used without further purification. Simulated Body Fluid (SBF) was prepared following the instructions in the literature.[22] Deionized water was Milli-Q purified (18.2 M Ω cm and < 6 ppb TOC). Different KH_2PO_4 / K_2HPO_4 (from Merck) phosphate buffered solutions (PBS) of 0.1 M ionic strength were used.

MG 63 osteoblast-like cells (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) were grown as monolayer in 75 cm² polystyrene flask containing cell culture medium (CCM) at 37 °C in a 5% CO₂ humidified atmosphere. CCM consisted of DMEM (Gibco, Germany) supplemented with 10 % v/v foetal bovine serum (Sigma-Aldrich), 1 % v/v of penicillin / streptomycin (Sigma-Aldrich). Cells were counted in an improved Neubauer hemocytometer and viability was determined by the exclusion Trypan blue (Sigma) assay.

2b. Preparation of 45S5 bioactive glass scaffolds

Highly porous scaffolds were prepared from 45S5 BG powder by using fully reticulated PU foams and the foam replica technology.[23] Briefly, the slurry for impregnation of the PU foams was prepared by dissolving 6% (w/v) of PVA in deionized water at 80°C. Then 45S5 BG powder was added to the PVA solution until the concentration was 40 wt %. Polyurethane foam (PU, 7×7×12 mm size) was then immersed in the slurry enabling glass particles to adhere uniformly to the surfaces of the PU foam. Scaffolds were then taken out from the slurry, the extra slurry was squeezed out manually, and the scaffolds were dried at 60 °C for 24 h. The coating procedure was repeated twice to achieve better mechanical properties. The samples were dried at 60 °C for 24 h and then sintered at 1100 °C for 3 h to obtain the BG-based scaffolds.

2c. Synthesis of hydroxyapatite nanoparticles with and without metal doping

Hydroxyapatite nanoparticles (HA) were obtained by an adaptation of the wet chemical deposition method [24]. Briefly, 15 mL of a solution containing 0.981 g H₃PO₄ was added drop-wise into 10 mL calcium hydroxide suspension (125 g L⁻¹) over a period of 120 min under constant stirring and heating at 80 °C. The mixture was then allowed to stand stirring at room temperature for one hour. The obtained HA was separated from the mother liquor by filtration with hydrophilic 0.22 µm pore membranes, washed several times with deionized water and dried at 80 °C for 24 h.

Loading of HA with either Mg²⁺, Zn²⁺, or both was performed during hydroxyapatite synthesis by adding the metal salt to the phosphoric acid solution prior to the mixing with Ca(OH)₂ to minimize the formation of metal oxides. Otherwise, the same procedure described previously for HA was followed keeping the Ca:P ratio in 1.67:1 and using Zn:Ca

and Mg:Ca mole ratios of 1:10 for obtaining one-metal-loaded HA (denoted as Zn-HA and Mg-HA, respectively) and of 0.5:10 for the bimetal loading with Zn and Mg (denoted as Mg-Zn-HA).

2.d Preparation of 45S5 bioactive glass scaffolds coated with hydroxyapatite nanoparticles

Coated-BG scaffolds were obtained by manual deep-coating. Different concentration of the particles suspensions and time of exposition were evaluated. The optimum conditions selected for the studies herein described were of 5 mg/ml nanoparticles and 10 minutes of exposition based on the criterion that a small fraction of the BG surface should remain uncovered to allow the direct contact of the BG surface with the biological environment. The coated scaffolds were dried at room temperature during 24 h.

2.e. Particle dissolution assays

1 mg/ml nanoparticles suspensions of either Zn-HA, Mg-HA or Mg-Zn-HA in PBS buffer of pH 7.4 were stirred and maintained at 37 °C during 1 and 7 days. After the incubation period, the particles were filtered with 0.22 µm pore hydrophilic filters and the filtrate acidified with nitric acid previous injection in a MP-AES spectrophotometer for metal quantification.

2.f Characterization methods

Details of standard *Equipment and Physicochemical assays* used for particle characterization, as XRD, HRTEM, SEM, and FTIR determinations and Fluorescence Microscopy are provided in the Supporting Information under the title “Equipment”.

The X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) spectra were obtained under UHV with a XR50 Specs GmbH spectrometer using Mg K(α) as the excitation source and a PHOIBOS 100 half sphere electron energy analyzer. A two-point calibration of the energy scale was performed

using sputtered cleaned gold (Au 4f7/2, binding energy (BE) 84.00 eV) and copper (Cu 2p3/2, BE: 932.67 eV) samples. Internal calibration to correct for surface charging was performed with the C 1s peak at BE= 284.6 eV due to adventitious carbon. High resolution XPS spectra were taken to get a better insight into the chemical environment of the different atoms. A Shirley-type background from each spectrum was used to remove the effect of the extrinsic structure loss and the spectrum resolved by Gaussian-Lorentzian fitting, keeping χ^2 to their minimum values.

Zn²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ion concentration was determined with a Microwave Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometer (MP-AES, Agilent MP-4200 AES). To that purpose, scaffolds and nanoparticles were digested with 10 mol/dm³ HNO₃ before analysis

2.g Mineralization assays

Hydroxyapatite formation on scaffolds was evaluated according to published procedures [25,26]. To that purpose, samples were immersed during for 1h, 1 d and 7 d in SBF in a shaking incubator at 120 rpm and 37 °C. Hydroxyapatite formation was observed by SEM, FTIR and XRD.

2.h. Biological assays

Scaffolds were sterilized with dry air at 160 °C and then preconditioned by immersion in CCM at 37 °C in a 5% CO₂ humidified atmosphere. The medium was changed every day until pH was lower than 8. Then, samples were washed with PBS and MG cells were grown on the scaffolds for 1 h at 37 °C before completing with CCM to the final volume of the well. The cell cultures were kept at 37 °C in a 5% CO₂ humidified atmosphere for incubation periods of 48 h and 7 days. The samples were then removed from the wells and placed in new wells to ensure that only cells attached to the scaffolds were

analysed. To evaluate possible interference between nanoparticles and the detection techniques, scaffolds without cells were used as controls. The viability was evaluated using WST-1 assay based in the mitochondrial dehydrogenases activity. MG-63 cells proliferation was evaluated by the BrdU-assay and attachment and cell morphology was observed by SEM. A description of the assays used may be found in the Supplementary Information under the title “Biological Assays”.

Each experiment was repeated 6 times and the results presented as the mean value \pm standard deviation. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA test and multiple comparisons were made using p values corrected according to the Bonferroni method.

3. Results and Discussion

3.a Nanoparticles characterization

High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (HRTEM) of HA (see Figure 1) show the formation of highly crystalline, rod-shaped nanoparticles with lattice spacing of *ca.* 0.34 nm in line with those reported for hydroxyapatite (002) planes.[27,28] Rods are of 10-20 nm width and between 50 – 100 nm long. Because of agglomeration, it is not possible to obtain a statistical distribution of their sizes.

TEM images and HRTEM images of Mg-HA and Mg-Zn-HA (see Figure 1 and S.I.) show agglomerated, highly crystalline, rod-shaped nanoparticles of 10-20 nm width and 50 – 100 nm long with lattice spacing of *ca.* 0.34 nm, in line with the morphological properties of unloaded HA [29]. Images of Zn-HA also show crystalline structure with 0.34 nm spacing, but observed nanorods seem smaller than those of the other nanoparticles. Moreover, selected-area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns of all nanoparticles confirmed the

characteristic HA patterns of (002) planes with distances of 0.344 nm. Only Zn-HA and HA samples show HA spacing of 0.816 nm characteristic of (011) planes.[30,31]

Figure 1: HRTEM images of similar magnification of HA, Mg-HA, Zn-HA and Mg-Zn-HA and magnified images of HA and Mg-Zn-HA showing the characteristic (011) plane separations of HA.

Diffraction patterns of HA, Zn-HA, Mg-HA and Mg-Zn-HA particles showed characteristic peaks of hydroxyapatite [32], as depicted in Figure 2 for Mg-Zn-HA powders and S.I for HA, Zn-HA and Mg-HA. Impurity phases such as α - and β -tricalcium phosphate (TCP), if present, are at very low levels as no contribution of TCP intense peaks at 2θ 30.5 - 31.6 are observed [33]. Moreover, the XRD analysis did not register the presence of co-crystallized salts within detectable limits of 1–3 wt%. These observations suggest that mainly hydroxyapatite crystalline domains are formed during the synthesis process, as desired.

EDX coupled with HRTEM (see Supporting Information EDX) confirmed the presence of Mg in Mg-HA, Zn in Zn-HA, and of both elements in Mg-Zn-HA samples, as also does the respective XPS spectrum.

Figure 2: XRD diffractogram of Mg-Zn-HA (black lines), Mg-Zn-HA-BG (blue lines), and Mg-Zn-HA-BG after 1 d immersion in SBF (red lines). * indicate peaks that may correspond to the hydroxyapatite lattice.

The XPS survey spectrum of all the samples depicts the main lines for Ca, O, and P, as well as the spurious C1s peak at 284.6 eV (see SI XPS). Ca 2p signals show Ca2p_{1/2} and Ca2p_{3/2} lines at 347.0 eV separated by 3.5 eV, and P2p_{1/2} and P2p_{3/2} lines at 133 eV separated by 0.9 eV, characteristic of apatite moieties. O1s signals (see Figure 3) show major contribution (between 65 to 76%) of a band at 531.3 eV assigned to oxygen atoms in phosphates, hydroxyl and adsorbed water [34] and less important contributions at 532.8 eV, which may be assigned to spurious organic matter and adsorbed carbonate. In fact, C1s signals of metal loaded and unloaded-HA, all show the contribution of C atoms in a carbonate environment at BE of 289.0 eV, see Supporting Information XPS.[35] However, due to the occurrence of spurious organic contamination, any quantitative analysis of this contribution to the C1s peak is subjected to a large error. Contributions due to MgO and ZnO at 530.0 eV cannot be

discarded,[36] as the peak area at this binding energy in Zn-HA, MgHA, and Mg-Zn-HA samples is increased with respect to that observed for metal-free HA, see Table 1.

Mg-HA and Zn-HA samples also showed signals due to Mg 1s and Zn 2p, respectively, while Mg-Zn-HA samples depict both signals, see Figure 3. Zn2p signals show significant split spin-orbit components with $\Delta = 23$ eV. Two contributions to the Zn2p_{3/2} region are observed: one with binding energy of 1022 eV which could be assigned to ZnO and a second contribution with 1023.4 eV characteristic of Zn²⁺ salts (NIST).[36] The percentage contribution of *ca.* 60% observed for ZnO and 40% for Zn²⁺ is maintained in both, Zn-HA and Mg-Zn-HA, nanoparticles as depicted in Table 1.

Figure 3: Zn2p, Mg1s and O1s XPS signals in Zn-HA, Mg-HA and Mg-Zn-HA samples. Dashed lines stand for the different contributions to the main signal.

Both, Mg-HA and Mg-Zn-HA nanoparticles show the contribution of peaks with BE of 1304.2 and 1305.5 eV to Mg1s signals, see Figure 3, attributed to MgO (*ca.* 35%) and Mg²⁺ salts (*ca.* 65%) (NIST), respectively, see Table 1. It may be therefore concluded, that the particles surface of both, Zn and Mg are partially oxidized. However, while MgO contribute by a 35% to the total incorporated Mg, ZnO contributes with a 60% to total incorporated Zn. Considering the experimental sensitivity factors for the different elements, surface ratios of P/Ca and O/Ca of 0.6 and 2.8 were determined for HA, in line with the theoretical expected values of 0.6 and 2.6, respectively. The increased P/Ca and O/Ca values (see Table 1) observed for Zn and Mg-modified apatite are in line with the substitution of Ca²⁺ ions by either Mg²⁺ or Zn²⁺. Moreover, ratios of (Ca+Zn+Mg)/P < 1.67 are indicative of calcium deficient apatite materials. (Ca+Zn+Mg)/P values of 1.55(±0.1) and 1.58(±0.1) observed for Zn-HA and Mg-Zn-HA indicate that any calcium deficiency in these materials is of little significance. Mg-HA samples showing (Ca+Zn+Mg)/P = 1.31(±0.1) might be assumed a calcium deficient apatite.[37]

Table 1: BE (in eV) and % contribution (in parenthesis) to O1s, Ca2p, P2p, Zn2p, and Mg1s XPS signals of HA, Zn-HA, Mg-HA, and Mg-Zn-HA nanoparticles. The amount of Zn and Mg given in ppm nanoparticle obtained by MP-AES are also shown.

	HA	Zn-HA	Mg-HA	Mg-Zn-HA
O1s	529.7 (< 8%)	529.9 (15%)	530.0 (14%)	530.6 (17%)
	531.0 (73%)	531.4 (76%)	531.2 (73%)	531.6 (65%)
	532.4 (19%)	533.0 (9%)	532.9 (13%)	532.9 (17%)
Zn	----	1022.3 (62%)	----	1022.6 (59%)
		1023.4 (38%)		1023.8 (41%)
Mg	----	----	1304.3 (35%)	1304.0 (37%)
			1305.6 (65%)	1305.3 (63%)
P/Ca	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.7
O/Ca	2.8	3.1	3.1	3.25
Zn:Ca	0	0.09	----	0.065
Mg:Ca	0	----	0.05	0.04
(Ca+Zn+Mg)/P	1.67(±0.1)	1.55(±0.1)	1.31(±0.1)	1.58(±0.1)
Zn (ppm)	non detectable	10800 ± 3000	-----	8000 ± 3000
Mg (ppm)	non detectable	-----	4600 ± 300	2800 ± 300

The amounts of incorporated Zn and Mg, depicted in Table 1 as ppm of sample are *ca.* 15-25% the values expected from the analytical concentration used in the respective synthesis procedures. A low incorporation of Mg²⁺ and Zn²⁺ ions in the HA lattice has been assigned in the literature to the distortion of the HA lattice due to the significantly smaller size of Mg²⁺ and Zn²⁺ with respect to Ca²⁺ ions (0.72, 0.74, and 0.99 Å ionic radii, respectively) causing bond strain and decreased crystallinity.[38]

The FTIR spectra of Zn-HA, Mg-HA and Mg-Zn-HA, as shown in Figures 4A and B, reveal the presence of typical PO₄³⁻ modes of the HA structure: asymmetric stretching at 1093 cm⁻¹ and 1024 cm⁻¹, symmetric stretching at 974 cm⁻¹, triply degenerate bending at 601 and 561 cm⁻¹, doubly degenerate bending at 478 cm⁻¹, and labile PO₄³⁻ at 634 cm⁻¹. [37] However, a decrease in relative peak intensities at 561, 601, and 1024 cm⁻¹ for Mg and Zn- loaded HA

as compared to HA, see Figure 4B, reflect a relative decrease in crystallinity with the addition of Mg^{2+} and Zn^{2+} , in line with literature reports.[39] However, this decrease is of lesser significance for Mg-Zn bi-loaded HA, as shown in Figure 4A. The small signal at 871 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the doubly degenerate CO_3^{2-} bending mode which indicates the formation of a β -type carbonate (substituting phosphates) in loaded and unloaded HA. Carbonate may arise from the synthesis procedure performed in alkaline solutions opened to the air.

The FTIR spectrum of Mg-Zn-HA depicts some small bands which are either absent or of less significance in Mg-HA, Zn-HA, and HA FTIR spectra (see Figure 4 *insets*). Bands appearing at around 3560 (broad), 1710, 1470, and 420 cm^{-1} are attributed to the stretching vibrations of OH units, to adsorbed water, to CO_3^{2-} stretching, and to ZnO vibrations, respectively, in line with reported data for biological apatite, Mg carbonates, and ZnO materials.[40–42] The latter observations strongly point to an enhanced hydrophilic, carbonated Mg-Zn-HA material also containing Zn oxide.

Dissolution studies of Zn-HA, Mg-HA and Mg-Zn-HA in PBS buffer suspensions of pH 7.4 showed that, Mg^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions were present in concentration $< 0.02\text{ ppm}$ in the dissolution filtrate after 7 days incubation, thus supporting a negligible dissolution of the ions from the particles.

Figure 4: FTIR spectrum of (A) Mg-Zn-HA (black line) and (B) Zn-HA (blue line) and Mg-HA (green line). The spectrum of HA (red line) is shown for comparison. The *Insets* show an expansion of the 3600 – 1300 cm⁻¹ region of the spectra in the main figure.

3.b Coated BG scaffolds characterization

Sintered scaffolds were of approximately 8.3 mm diameter and 4.3 mm thick, as observed in the optical microscope image of Mg-Zn-HA shown in Figure 5 A. The porosity of uncoated BG and coated scaffolds was between 92-94%, as estimated from optical microscope images following literature procedures [23], thus indicating that surface modification did not change the macroscopic porosity on the scaffolds. However, SEM images of nanoparticle-coated scaffolds (see Figure 5B for uncoated BG and Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds and S.I for the other coated scaffolds) show that nanoparticle coating changed the morphology of the original BG surface. In fact, the nanorod-shaped metal-loaded and unloaded HA nanoparticles deposited on the BG surface are observed to form a microporous irregular layer with some free BG surface.

(A)

(B)

Figure 5: (A) Optical microscope image of Mg-Zn-HA - coated BG scaffold. (B) SEM images of uncoated BG and Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffold. Magnification of 500, 10.0, and 50.0 X are shown from left to right.

XRD diffractograms of uncoated scaffolds (see Figure 2 and S.I. XRD) suggest highly crystalline powders with matching angular location and relative intensity of the peaks to those of the crystal- line phase of $\text{Na}_2\text{Ca}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_9$, observed in standard PDF #22.1455.[43] The presence of HA in coated BG samples could not be observed by XRD probably due to the low fraction of nanoparticle coverage of BG scaffolds.

The amount of Zn, as obtained by MP-AES, in Zn-HA-BG and Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds was of 870 ± 250 and 1040 ± 300 ppm scaffold. Considering the latter values and the individual Zn content in the nanoparticles (10800 and 8000 ppm particles, respectively, see Table 1), the scaffold coverage with nanoparticles is of *ca.* 8 and 13% w/w for Zn-HA-BG and Mg-Zn-HA-BG, respectively. The low scaffold coverage with Mg-HA and the error in the determination, precluded a reliable estimate of the Mg-HA coverage of BG scaffolds.

3.c Mineralization Assays

Scaffolds were immersed during 1h, 1 day and 7 days in SBF at 37 °C and then analysed by SEM, FTIR and XRD to observe the formation and deposition of hydroxyapatite layers. SEM images obtained after 1 day of Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds incubation (see Figure 6) already show the formation and homogeneous dense coverage of cauliflower-like structures characteristic of calcium phosphate precipitates.[44,45] For uncoated BG, Zn-HA-BG and Mg-HA-BG scaffolds, dense coverage with cauliflower-like calcium phosphate structures was observed after 7 days of incubation, thus indicating that the mineralization process is faster for Mg-Zn-HA-coated BG samples.

The FTIR spectra of samples before and after 1 d immersion in SBF show peak differences strongly confirming the deposition of calcium phosphate on the scaffolds surface. In fact, 45S5 bioactive glass IR spectrum shows characteristic sharp peaks at 440, 520 and 620 cm^{-1} attributed to Si-O-Si bending in the crystalline phase.[46] Peaks at 1015 and 1088 cm^{-1} are attributed to Si-O-Si stretching vibrations[47,48] while the peak at 915 cm^{-1} is assigned to the vibrational mode of Si-O with a non-bridging oxygen[47,49] formed in the glass network as a consequence of Ca^{2+} and Na^+ modifiers. Upon immersion of BG scaffolds in SBF, a peak at *ca.* 1015 cm^{-1} due to P-O stretching of phosphate groups is overlapped to that of Si-O-Si which grows with the immersion time as observed in Figure 6.[49,50] Moreover, after 7 days of immersion in SBF, the intensity of BG peaks at 520, 620, and 915 cm^{-1} is reduced and new peaks at 570 and 600 cm^{-1} are observed and attributed to bending vibrations of P-O in crystalline hydroxyapatite.[37] The latter observations strongly indicate important changes in the scaffolds composition and in particular at its surface, in line with the thick layer of cauliflower calcium phosphate deposited on the BG surface observed by SEM.

Figure 6: SEM images of (from top to down) BG, HA-BG, and Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds after 1 and 7 days incubation in SBF at 37 °C. Magnification is 10.0X. Corresponding FTIR spectra are also shown, where the black, blue and red curves stand for the corresponding spectrum before and after 1 and 7 days immersion in SBF, respectively.

The FTIR spectra of HA-BG, Zn-HA-BG and Mg-HA-BG scaffolds show similar behaviour than those described for BG (see Figure 6 and S.I. Mineralization Assays) exhibiting a dense

coverage with cauliflower-like calcium phosphate structures after 7 d immersion. However, Mg-Zn-HA-BG samples showed deposition of cauliflower calcium phosphate already at 1 h immersion and a clear enhanced deposition after 1 d immersion when compared to uncoated BG, HA-BG, Zn-HA-BG and Mg-HA-BG samples, as may be observed in Figure 6 and in S.I. FTIR results. Moreover, crystalline hydroxyapatite characteristic XRD peak at 2θ of 31.2° is only observed in the XRD diffractogram of Mg-Zn-HA-BG sample taken after 1 day immersion in SBF (see Figure 2) but is absent in that of 1 d immersed uncoated BG scaffold (see S.I. XRD). Since the mineralization process is favoured by appropriate nucleation centres and/or particle dissolution,[51] the fast rate of mineralization observed for Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds suggests that Mg-Zn-HA could act as nucleation centre and/or favour the process due to the simultaneous dissolution of Zn and Mg ions.

3.d Cell Culture Viability

Figure 7 shows SEM images of the scaffolds after 2 days preconditioning. Uncoated BG, HA-BG, Mg-HA-BG and Zn-HA-BG samples show homogeneously-covered surfaces except for the presence of well-defined hexagonal inorganic precipitates on HA-BG. Merely Mg-Zn-HA-BG pre-conditioned scaffolds show more irregular topology with well-defined cauliflower-like calcium phosphate structures.

Figure 7: SEM images (10 Kx magnification) of 2 days preconditioned BG, HA-BG, Mg-HA-BG, Zn-HA-BG and Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds in cell culture medium at 37°C .

MG-63 cells viability in the presence of coated and uncoated BG scaffolds was evaluated using the WST-1 assay based in the mitochondrial dehydrogenase activity and the

BrdU-assay evaluating cell proliferation after 2 and 7 days. Cell attachment and morphology was observed by SEM.

Results from WST-1 assay are summarized in Figure 8A. No significant differences were found in cells grown on HA-BG, Mg-HA-BG, and Zn-HA-BG scaffolds with respect to control (uncoated BG). However, for Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds a significant increase in cell viability ($p < 0.05$) was observed after 2 and 7 days incubation.

BrdU-assay results (see Figure 8B) show a significant increment with respect to controls in cell proliferation for MG-63 cell cultures in the presence of Mg-Zn-HA-BG after 2 ($p < 0.05$) and 7 days ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 8: (A) WST-1 assay results performed for MG-63 cell cultures after 2 and 7 days in the presence of Mg-HA-BG, Zn-HA-BG and Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds, expressed as control (uncoated BG) percentage. (B) BrdU- assay results in MG-63 cell cultures after 2 and 7 days in the presence of Mg-Zn-HA-BG expressed as control (uncoated BG) percentage. *, ** and *** indicate significant differences with $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, and $p < 0.001$, respectively. All the data are expressed as mean \pm SD, $n = 6$.

SEM images (Figure 9) of cultured MG63 osteoblast-like cells on Mg-Zn-HA-BG and uncoated BG scaffolds after 2 and 7 days incubation, showed that cells remained in a spread morphology and with a high interconnection between them in both scaffolds. Moreover, cells on Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds already present a high connection with the surface material after 2 days incubation. MG63 cells on uncoated BG scaffolds do not show significant connections after 2 and 7 days. The interconnections between cells and scaffolds exhibit adhesion contacts and microfilament fibre bundles, as observed in Figure 9. In summary, biological assays clearly demonstrate that coating of BG scaffolds with Mg-Zn-HA leads to an enhanced osteoblastic MG-63 cell culture viability and proliferation with a high interconnection between cells and the scaffold surface. Coating with HA, Zn-HA or Mg-HA does not seem to enhance BG scaffold interaction with MG-63 cells.

Figure 9: SEM images of MG-63 cell culture samples after 2 and 7 days incubation in the presence of Mg-Zn-HA-BG and BG scaffolds.

4. Discussion

Metal-loaded hydroxyapatite composites containing either Mg^{2+} or Zn^{2+} or both metal ions were synthesized and thoroughly characterized. All nanoparticles (HA, Mg-HA, Zn-HA, and Mg-Zn-HA) were rod-shaped of 10-20 nm width and 50 – 100 nm long, with lattice spacing of *ca.* 0.34 nm, in line with reported HA patterns. XRD patterns of metal-loaded HA mainly show HA crystalline domains, probably due to the low incorporation of Zn and Mg ions. In fact, XPS and MP-AES data suggest < 1% w/w incorporation of metal ions, which, depending of the particle type may be both, partly oxidized or incorporated on the HA lattice. In this sense, Zinc is *ca.* 60% as ZnO while Mg oxidation to MgO accounts to a 35%. The presence of ZnO and MgO seems not to affect the biological behavior of the coated scaffolds, in agreement with literature reports indicating that inclusion of 0.5 wt% MgO in pure hydroxyapatite significantly enhanced the grain growth and the mechanical properties of HA while maintaining biocompatibility (MTT assay).[52]

45S5 BG scaffolds were successfully coated with less than 10% w/w of metal-loaded HA. The scaffolds' 3D pore structure remained invariant after coating, as assessed by SEM. After 7 days immersion of HA, Zn-HA and Mg-HA –coated BG scaffolds in SBF, the formation of a dense layer of cauliflower-like calcium phosphate structures matching that formed on unmodified BG is observed. Moreover, HA-BG, Zn-HA-BG and Mg-HA-BG scaffolds also show comparable bioactivity and biocompatibility to that of unmodified BG. Therefore, results from *in vitro* biological assays seem to indicate that surface modification of BG with HA, Mg-HA or Zn-HA does not bring particular benefits when using these materials as scaffolds for tissue engineering purposes with respect to unmodified BG. However, since ZnO-coated HA has been reported to show excellent antibacterial efficacy against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* strains due to ZnO release of Zn^{2+} ions and

generation of reactive oxygen species, the antibacterial potential of the Zn-HA-BG scaffolds is a further interesting property that deserves investigation.[53]

Interestingly, Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds were capable of forming a dense layer of calcium phosphate structures already after 2 d incubation in biological relevant media, as well as a significant increase in biocompatibility and proliferative properties with respect to uncoated BG and HA-BG scaffolds. Formation of calcium phosphate structures and adhesion of cells are important parameters determining the interaction of a material with bone tissue. Our results are in line with literature reports pointing the advantages of biological apatite in enamel, dentin and bone where trace amounts of Mg and Zn are known to stimulate bone formation and the enhancement of bone-cell interaction.[39] The importance of Mg and Zn dual-doping with respect to mono metal doping in enhancing cell proliferation has also been reported for TCP and assigned to an improvement of the mechanical properties and cell-material interactions.[54] Also, co-implanted dual Zn and Mg ions on titanium surface were found to promote initial adhesion and spreading of rat bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells via the upregulation of the gene expressions of integrin, among other multiple functions.[12] The decrease in crystallinity due to the incorporation of Mg and Zn in the HA lattice is reported to increase HA nanoparticles dissolution in the physiological environment.[39] Also, BG ionic dissolution products have been reported to further stimulate osteogenesis and angiogenesis by the enhanced expression of genes in cells, leading to bone formation and vascularization.[55] Since we have not observed detectable dissolution of metals from Mg-Zn-HA after 7 days immersion in PBS of pH 7.4, the enhanced intrinsic bioactivity of the Mg-Zn-HA-coated bioactive glass scaffold cannot be attributed to an enhanced metal dissolution. However, due to the low %w and the opened microporous sublayer of metal-loaded-HA and HA covering the BG scaffold structure, it is expected that the ionic

dissolution products of the BG structure is still possible, as may be concluded from the fact that Zn-HA-BG, Mg-HA-BG, HA-BG and uncoated BG scaffolds, all show similar *in vitro* biological response.

The biological response to artificial materials depends on many parameters other than ion dissolution, such as chemical composition, topography, porosity and grain size.[56] It is known from the literature that osteoblasts attach to a surface through a morphology-dependent mechanism. Osteoblasts focal adhesion contacts and microfilament stress-fiber bundles were reported to occur in microtextured surfaces even in the absence of exogenous adhesive proteins that can facilitate osteoblast adhesion.[57] Preconditioned BG and Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds present different surface topology, being that of Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds more irregular and microstructured than that of uncoated BG, probably leading to the generation of new nucleation sites favoring cell attachment and therefore viability. These nucleation sites might be more hydrophilic and carbonated, as inferred from the comparison of the IR spectra of unloaded and loaded HA.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, the good *in vitro* response observed in this work for Mg-Zn-HA-BG scaffolds opens the possibility for future extended studies on their biological behavior *in vivo* as potentially antibacterial scaffolding material and provides a well-founded basis for considering this newly developed biomaterial as a valid alternative for further investigations in this field.

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